

THE ROLE OF SMALL ARCHITECTURAL FORM GAZEBOS IN THE DESIGN OF RECREATION GARDENS

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Annotation: Gazebos are an integral part of recreational parks: they not only provide comfort for people but also enhance the aesthetic appearance of the area. Properly designed and positioned gazebos make any park more attractive and functional. Therefore, when designing and constructing small architectural forms, particularly gazebos, it is important to combine modern requirements, national traditions, and ecological approaches. Gazebos created based on modern approaches support environmental sustainability and make the urban environment more appealing.

Keywords: gazebo, pavilion, pergola, rotunda, arcade, fountain, bench, porch, gallery, monument, atrium, walkway, round and oval shapes, energy-saving technologies, environmental sustainability, "green architecture."

Introduction. In a period when modern urban planning and landscape architecture are developing, recreation gardens are gaining particular importance as places for people to relax, unwind, and harmonize with nature. In the organization of such areas, small architectural forms occupy an important place. Among these forms, gazebos (open or semi-enclosed recreational pavilions) are considered one of the most widely used and aesthetically significant elements. Gazebos are light-structured recreational constructions of an open or semi-enclosed type, which are widely used in recreation gardens. Their main function is to protect visitors from sunlight, rain, and wind, as well as to create comfortable conditions for отдых. At the same time, gazebos also serve as spaces for social interaction.

Gazebos are often equipped with benches, tables, and sometimes decorative elements. This makes them suitable not only for relaxation but also for family gatherings, conversations, and small events.

Main part. In the process of modern urbanization, creating a comfortable ecological environment for the urban population is considered one of the important tasks. In particular, recreation gardens serve as essential spaces for people's physical and mental relaxation. In the effective organization of these areas, small architectural forms have special significance. Small architectural forms are an important component of landscape architecture, serving to decorate the area, enrich it functionally, and create convenience for users. One of such elements is gazebos.

The architectural solutions of gazebos vary, and they are selected in accordance with the overall landscape design of the area. The most common forms include:

- circular and oval shapes;
- rectangular and square shapes;
- polygonal (hexagonal or octagonal) shapes.

The roof structure can also be of different types: domed, pyramidal, or flat roofs. When choosing materials, climatic conditions, economic factors, and aesthetic requirements are taken

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into account. Wooden gazebos provide a sense of naturalness and warmth, while metal structures ensure strength and modernity.

When placing gazebos, their harmony with the surrounding environment is of great importance. They are usually installed in the following locations:

- near water bodies;
- in wooded areas;
- at the intersections of pedestrian pathways;
- in central squares.

Such placement not only enhances the aesthetic appearance but also increases convenience for users. Additionally, gazebos can serve as either a central or a secondary element of the landscape composition.

Gazebos are lightweight structures designed for short-term relaxation, conversation, or enjoying natural scenery. They are usually made of wood, metal, concrete, or combined materials. The main functions of gazebos are to provide shade, ensure comfortable seating, and add decorative value to the area.

In recreation gardens, gazebos come in various shapes and designs. The most common forms are circular, rectangular, hexagonal, and octagonal. Their roof can be domed, مخروط-shaped, or flat. When selecting a design, the overall architectural style of the area, landscape characteristics, and functional requirements are taken into account. When placing gazebos, their harmony with the surrounding environment is important. For example, gazebos built near water bodies become more attractive from a scenic point of view. Likewise, gazebos located in the shade of trees create a cool environment during hot summer days. Gazebos placed at the intersections of pathways or in central squares become convenient resting points for visitors.

Small architectural forms and their definitions

№	Name	Definition
1	Gazebo	Open or semi-enclosed, light-structured building intended for rest and relaxation.
2	Pavilion	A light building constructed in gardens and park areas for temporary rest or holding events.
3	Pergola	An open passageway or canopy consisting of columns and a lattice roof, intended for plant growth.
4	Rotunda	A circular architectural structure surrounded by columns and covered with a dome.
5	Column	A vertical supporting element that holds up a roof or other structure.

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№	Name	Definition
6	Arch	A curved structure used in entrances or passageways.
7	Arcade	A closed or semi-open passage formed by a series of arches.
8	Balcony	An open platform extending from the exterior wall of a building.
9	Terrace	An open recreation area, often located on an elevated place.
10	Fountain	A decorative structure consisting of flowing water and ornamental elements.
11	Bench	A simple furniture element intended for sitting.
12	Lamp post	A tall pole-mounted lighting device used to illuminate an area.
13	Fence	A barrier used to separate or protect an area.
14	Gate	An opening and closing structure providing access to an area.
15	Pathway	A special path intended for pedestrian movement.
16	Small bridge	A structure built for crossing small water bodies or obstacles.
17	Sculpture	A three-dimensional artwork created as a form of artistic expression.
18	Obelisk	A tall stone monument that narrows upward in shape.
19	Monument	A structure built to commemorate a historical event or person.
20	Canopy	A lightweight roof structure covering entrances or passageways.
21	Atrium	An internal open or enclosed central courtyard of a building.
22	Gallery	A space used for displaying artworks or serving as an enclosed passageway.

As a small architectural form, gazebos have not only a functional but also an aesthetic significance. They enrich the overall composition of the garden and give rhythm and harmony to the landscape. In modern design, minimalism, national style, and ecological approaches are widely used. For example, wooden gazebos decorated with national patterns give the area a distinctive cultural spirit.

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Figure 1. Monuments and gazebos in recreation gardens.

In the design of gazebos, issues of ergonomics and comfort are also important. The height of the seating, the width of the roof, the level of ventilation, and the lighting system should be carefully considered. In particular, comfortable access paths and adaptive design elements must be provided for people with disabilities.

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Currently, the trend of using ecological materials is increasing. Gazebos made of wood, bamboo, and recycled materials correspond to the principles of sustainable development without harming nature. In addition, modern gazebos equipped with solar panels also provide energy-saving opportunities. Zamonaviy besedkalarni loyihalashda The human factor is of primary importance. The height of the seating, the width of the roof covering, the level of ventilation, and the lighting system must meet ergonomic requirements, and safety issues are also important. The structural durability, the quality of materials, and fire resistance must be taken into account.

Nowadays, ecological and innovative approaches are widely used in the construction of gazebos. The use of recycled materials, the introduction of energy-saving technologies, and adherence to the principles of “green architecture” are highly relevant.

For example, gazebos equipped with solar panels can generate energy. In addition, roofs covered with green plants improve the microclimate and enhance the aesthetic appearance of the area.

Conclusion gazebos are an integral part of recreation gardens, providing comfort for people while also enhancing the aesthetic appearance of the area. Properly designed and positioned gazebos make any garden more attractive and functional. Therefore, in the design and construction of small architectural forms, especially gazebos, it is important to combine modern requirements, national traditions, and ecological approaches. Gazebos created on the basis of modern approaches support environmental sustainability and make the urban environment more attractive.

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